

The determinants of job satisfaction and workplace spirituality of SHSP faculty members

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Abstract

Teaching has been one of the most significant and respectable professions of our time. Helping students achieve and fulfill their dreams can be a truly rewarding experience although most of the time it can be daunting particularly in the field of health science courses. Facing the tedious task of teaching students, a health science faculty professor must be holistically satisfied with their fundamental role in order for them to live and stay longer in this modest profession. Job satisfaction has been a supremely important issue in higher educational institutions nowadays due to several factors such as the fast changing environment, strict competition, meager compensation, and the high cost associated with hiring new talents. In recent times, organizations had been clamoring for the discussion of spirituality specifically in the workplace. This emerging theme is soaring in importance recently due to it clearly points organizational and individual benefits and how it may contribute in the betterment of an organization. Due to fast-paced changing environment particularly in the field of academe, the researcher was able to formulate the research question: Does workplace spirituality still have a place in St. Dominic College of Asia? In addition, due to the vast responsibilities assigned and given to SDCA faculty members, the researcher would also like to ask if what the faculty makes satisfied with their current work. With the following questions, the researcher was able to formulate the purpose of the study. This study aimed to determine the workplace spirituality and the factors affecting job satisfaction of the School of Health Science Professions faculty members particularly investigating if their workplace spirituality influences the factors affecting their job satisfaction. The study utilized a descriptive correlational design that aims to describe the relationship between the determinants of job satisfaction and perceived workplace spirituality of the full-time faculty members of the health science department. This study utilized a developed self-made questionnaire which has three parts: first is obtaining demographic characteristics, second is enumerating the nine (9) most influential determinants of job satisfaction and the last part consists of 10 items concerning the views of the respondents in terms of their perceived workplace spirituality while working at the institution. The results of the study illustrate that the most important factor that affects their job satisfaction is compensation (1st), followed by relationship with managers / supervisors (2nd), then relationship with coworkers (3rd), nature of work (4th), benefits and rewards (5th), training and development (6th), safety at the workplace (7th), promotion (8th), and lastly is management recognition (9th). The study also showed that the perceived workplace spirituality of health science professors were very high. The findings suggest that establishing a harmonious relationship with co-workers and managers shows a strong correlation with workplace spirituality ($\rho(11) = -.087, p < 0.01$). Furthermore, workplace spirituality and promotion also depict a strong correlation ($\rho(11) = .703, p < 0.01$). Weak correlation has been seen in the relationship between workplace spirituality and training and development ($\rho(11) = .253, p < 0.01$). The study mainly recommends improving the current and existing workplace spirituality both in the organizational and individual levels which will help employees feel that they are working in the right place and for the right institution.

Keywords: Faculty members; Workplace spirituality; Job satisfaction; Spirituality; Compassion; Meaningful work; Health Science Professions.

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Introduction

Teaching has been one of the most significant and respectable professions of our time. Helping students achieve and fulfill their dreams can be a truly rewarding experience, although most of the time it can be daunting, particularly in the field of health science courses. Nowadays, a health science faculty is not just helping future health care professionals understand their role in the industry but also assisting them to be emotionally inclined toward their chosen profession. It can be tiring and gruesome for some faculty members, particularly teaching unmotivated students who were forced to take the course due to rewarding careers in foreign countries. Facing the tedious task of teaching students, a health science faculty professor must be holistically satisfied with their fundamental role in order for them to live and stay longer in this modest profession.

Job satisfaction has been a supremely important issue in higher educational institutions nowadays due to several factors, such as the fast-changing environment, strict competition, meager compensation, and the high cost associated with hiring new talents (Mitchell et al., 2001). Many studies have already stated that employees' job satisfaction will produce superior quality performance in optimal time, which will lead to growing profits for organizations (Romig et al., 2011). Studies showed that satisfied professionals were also more likely to be innovative, creative, and provide ground-breaking ideas, which allowed companies to grow even in changing and challenging market conditions. In relation to academics, the satisfaction of faculty members who have that vital and overwhelming responsibility to take care of students is seen to be very crucial to the success of an academic organization.

In recent times, organizations have been clamoring for the discussion of spirituality, specifically in the workplace (Thompson, 2000). Organizations see this emerging theme as positive and vital for the success of their organizations. As defined, a person's search for the meaning of life, his or her place in the universe, and connection to the sacred or transcendent is often referred to as one's spirituality. This quest may or may not result in the creation of rituals or religious practices or the development of a sense of community (King & Koenig, 2009). The society believed that spirituality could intervene in all the crucial aspects of work life, particularly developing crucial characteristics such as altruism, love, care, and affection that lead to beneficial and positive outcomes (Wong, 2003). In terms of workplace spirituality, studies have defined it more than seventy times, although it has yet to be universally defined (Markow & Klenke, 2005). This refers to the various ways in which workers exhibit their spirituality at work, both for self-support and for making morally and justifiable decisions. It is also about caring, being compassionate, and giving support to others. It involves the integrity of an individual and people being true to themselves and to others (Smith, 2006).

Spirituality in the workplace, from the perspective of the organization, refers to an organizational culture that is supported by mission statements, leadership, and business practices that are socially and value-driven, that values the contributions of employees, and that promotes individual spiritual growth and well-being (Ashmos & Duchan, 2000; Guillory, 1997; Mitroff & Denton, 2012). From an individual perspective, spirituality at work can be defined as *“the recognition that employees have an inner life that is nourished by meaningful work, which takes place in the context of community”* (Ashmos & Duchon, 2000). It becomes evident that the leitmotif of workplace spirituality is the pursuit of purpose and contribution through work, as well as connectedness and authenticity at work. With the current, constant, and abrupt changes in the working landscape and the looming fear of employees, It is believed that employees who find purpose and meaning in their lives will be more likely to be committed to their organization (Milliman et al., 2003).

Due to the fast-paced changing environment, particularly in the field of academia, the researcher was able to formulate the research question: *Does workplace spirituality still have a place at St. Dominic College of Asia?* In addition, due to the vast responsibilities assigned and given to SDCA faculty members, the researcher would also like to ask if the faculty is satisfied with their current work. With the following questions, the researcher was able to formulate the purpose of the study: This study aimed to determine the workplace spirituality and the factors affecting job satisfaction of the School of Health Science Professions faculty members, particularly if their workplace spirituality influences the factors affecting their job satisfaction.

Methodology

This study was a quantitative type of research. The study used the descriptive-correlational method to determine the relationship between the profile variables of the respondents, workplace spirituality, and determinants of job satisfaction. The study described the profile variables of the teaching personnel of the health science department, which were age, gender, civil status, number of years working for the institution, and their religion. Furthermore, it describes the workplace spirituality and determinants of job satisfaction of health science professors. Respondents were asked to rank the most important to the least important job satisfaction determinant. In addition, the profile variables, workplace spirituality, and the determinants of job satisfaction were correlated with one another. The researchers utilized a self-made questionnaire for the respondents, which was designed to determine the workplace spirituality at SDCA. The survey tool was formulated based on a review of literature both locally and internationally. The tool has three parts: (a) the demographic profile of the respondents; (b) determinants of job satisfaction, which stated nine (9) most commonly stated factors affecting the job satisfaction of employees; and (c) the perceived workplace spirituality at SDCA. The last part has 10 questions and was measured using a five-point Likert scale from strongly agree to strongly disagree.

Reliability and Validity

A pilot test of the developed instrument was performed. Four (4) part-time faculty members affiliated with the department were chosen to determine the reliability of the instrument. Regarding the use of Cronbach's alpha reliability analysis, the tool had a satisfactory reliability index (0.87). Three senior top-level managers of the institution determined the face validity. Their suggestions for improving the readability, clarity, and conciseness of the perception statements were taken into account (Kupahu, 2017).

Percentages of the total number of participants were used to compute and report the responses to each question. A spreadsheet was used to collect data, which was then exported to statistical software (SPSS). For the purpose of creating sample profiles and summarizing the data, simple descriptive statistics were produced. Means and standard deviations were also computed for the Likert scale items to determine the perception of faculty members about workplace spirituality and job satisfaction (Kupahu, 2017). The Spearman correlation was utilized to determine the relationship between determinants of job satisfaction and perceived workplace spirituality.

Results and Discussion

A total of 13 faculty members of the School of Health Science Professions participated in the research study. Table 1 shows the distribution of the respondents in terms of their demographic data. In terms of age, most of the full time faculty members of the SHSP department belong to the age group 45 years old and above [$f = 5$; (38.46%)]. It was followed by the young adult group 21 – 27 years old and 33 – 44 years old [$f = 3$; (23.08%)]. Two [$f = 2$; (15.38%)] faculty members were part of the 28 – 32 age

group. In gender distribution, the masculine population dominates the population of the faculty in SHSP department [$f = 10$; (76.92%)]. The female teaching personnel of the department consist of three members [$f = 3$; (23.08%)]. In reporting the marital status, both single and married faculty equally represented the teaching population of the health science department [$f = 6$; (46.15%)]. A faculty reported that he is currently separated with his partner [$f = 1$; (7.70%)]. The respondents reported that most of the faculty are still considered young and new in working for the institution [$f = 9$; (69.23%)]. Senior full time faculty represent the second largest group in the department [$f = 3$; (23.07%)]. A faculty reported that she is now currently serving the institution for more than 5 years [$f = 1$; (7.70%)]. In terms of their spiritual belief and orientation, most of the faculty reported that they belong to the major religious organization in the country which is Roman Catholic [$f = 7$; (53.84%)]. Christian faculty members represent the second largest group in the department [$f = 3$; (23.07%)]. Iglesia ni Cristo, Muslim, and Protestant were also represented by a faculty member of the health science department [$f = 1$; (7.70%)].

Table 1. Demographic data of the respondents (N=13)

Characteristics	Variable	Frequency	%
Age (years)	21 – 27 years old	3	23.08
	28 – 32 years old	2	15.38
	33 – 44 years old	3	23.08
	45 years old and above	5	38.46
Gender	Male	10	76.92
	Female	3	23.08
Civil Status	Single	6	46.15
	Married	6	46.15
	Separated	1	7.70
Number of years working in SDCA	Less than 5 years	9	69.23
	5 – 10 years	1	7.70
	More than 10 years	3	23.07
Religion	Roman Catholic	7	53.84
	Iglesia ni Cristo	1	7.70
	Born Again Christian	3	23.06
	Muslim	1	7.70
	Others	1	7.70

Table 2 presents the ranking of the stated determinants that lead an employee to be satisfied with his or her job. It also shows the most important to least important determinant of job satisfaction among SHSP faculty members. The most important factor for health science professors is compensation (1st), followed by relationships with managers and supervisors (2nd), relationships with coworkers (3rd), nature of work (4th), benefits and rewards (5th), training and development (6th), safety at the workplace (7th), promotion (8th), and lastly, management recognition (9th). The table shows that most faculty members still feel the need for the right pay or cost for their rendered services. As literature has stated, one of the most important issues for employees, particularly teaching personnel, is the meager pay that they are receiving. As research studies have shown, several elements or factors that affect the job satisfaction of employees are compensation, promotion, benefits, work nature, supervision, and relationships with colleagues (Odembo, 2013; Muchemi, 2012). Studies also revealed that among the strongest predictors of job satisfaction were good pay and reward systems (Malik, 2011), work itself and advancement (Malik, 2010; Mangi et al., 2011), and adequate recognition and feeling of accomplishment (Oyewobi et al., 2012). Reed (2006) also identified and emphasized that the creation of a harmonious workplace that will encourage the retention of important faculty resources depends heavily on the determinants of faculty job satisfaction. It was also worth noting that SHSP faculty members see that harmonious relationships with their superiors and co-workers are very crucial for them to be satisfied with the current work. The professors also see that receiving recognition from management is the least important factor that affects their satisfaction with work.

Table 2. Determinants of job satisfaction based from importance

Determinants of Job Satisfaction	Total Mean Score	Ranking
Compensation	7.92	1st
Relationship with managers / supervisors	6.31	2nd
Relationship with co-workers	5.69	3rd
Nature of work	5.38	4th
Benefits and Rewards	4.85	5th
Training and development	4.77	6th
Safety at the workplace	4.62	7th
Promotion	3.00	8th
Management recognition	2.46	9th

In Table 3, it presents the perceived workplace spirituality of the SHSP faculty members. The teaching personnel reported that they experienced very high workplace spirituality while working in the institution (total mean score = 4.45). Statement number 9 received the highest mean score (4.69), which shows that their spiritual values influence their personal and professional decisions. This was followed by statement number 1 (4.54), which states the faculty sees the academic institution as their home away from home. This shows that they are very at ease and comfortable working for the institution. The item that received the lowest mean score came from statement number 10 (4.23), which explained the faculty members’ perceptions regarding the organization’s responsibility to take care of its employees. Several studies have noted that an organization that treats its employees as part of its community and emotionally connects to them will lead to the motivation and loyalty of the employees of the company and will create better organizational performance (Aravamudhan & Krishnaveni, 2014). Additionally, studies have found a connection between workplace spirituality and employee attitudes, including commitment to the company, intrinsic job satisfaction, and involvement in work (Milliman et al., 2003). In a locally published study regarding spirituality in the workplace, it was proved that spirituality is incarnated through organizational formations, environmental factors, and personal factors. It added that this spirituality is very essential for employees to feel and experience happiness at work. The study also emphasized that spirituality in the workplace may help employees thoroughly understand the true meaning of their role.

Table 3. Perceived workplace spirituality of SHSP faculty members (N=13)

Workplace Spirituality	Mean Score	Interpretation
1. I feel that my immediate workplace is my second home, and everyone treats each other as a member of the family.	4.54	Very High Workplace Spirituality
2. My superiors encourage my personal and professional growth.	4.62	Very High Workplace Spirituality
3. In my workplace, people are encouraged to discuss personal and work related problems.	4.38	Very High Workplace Spirituality
4. In my workplace, whenever there are issues, concerns and conflicts, people try to resolve it in a benevolent way.	4.38	Very High Workplace Spirituality
5. In my work I am evaluated fairly based on my performance.	4.46	Very High Workplace Spirituality
6. I experience joy and contentment in my work, and I share that joy and feeling of fulfilment to others.	4.31	Very High Workplace Spirituality
7. The current work I do is connected with what I think is important in my life.	4.54	Very High Workplace Spirituality
8. My current work helps me to energize my spiritual wellbeing.	4.31	Very High Workplace Spirituality
9. My spiritual values influence the choices and decisions I make in my personal and professional life.	4.69	Very High Workplace Spirituality

10. I feel that my organization prioritizes the welfare of its employees.	4.23	Very High Workplace Spirituality
Total Mean Score	4.45	Very High Workplace Spirituality

A Spearman’s correlation was run to determine the relationship between the nine determinants of job satisfaction and the workplace spirituality of the respondents. To determine correlations between the variables, the following interpretation will be utilized: greater than 0.7 = strong relationship; 0.3 and 0.7 = moderate; and less than 0.3 = weak. The findings suggest that establishing a harmonious relationship with co-workers and managers shows a strong correlation with workplace spirituality (rho(11): -.087, p <.001). Furthermore, workplace spirituality and promotion also depict a strong correlation (rho(11):.703, p <.001). A weak correlation has been seen in the relationship between workplace spirituality and training and development (rho(11):.253, p <.001). A local study reported that crucial factors for the satisfaction of teachers were school policies, supervision, pay, interpersonal relations, opportunities for promotion and growth, working conditions, work itself, achievement, recognition, and responsibility (Usop et al., 2013). Pilarta’s (2015) study also added that the job satisfaction of teachers in a state university was related to interpersonal relationships, financial and physical resources of the school, and supervision. Specifically, the teachers were satisfied with achievement, promotion, and professional growth and dissatisfied with their recognition and supervision.

Table 4. Spearman’s correlation between determinants of job satisfaction and workplace spirituality

Variables	Correlation Coefficient	Interpretation
Workplace Spirituality and Compensation	- 0.50	Very High Workplace Spirituality
Workplace Spirituality and Relationship with Coworkers	-.087	Very High Workplace Spirituality
Workplace Spirituality and Relationship with Managers	-.087	Very High Workplace Spirituality
Workplace Spirituality and Safety at Workplace	-.505	Very High Workplace Spirituality
Workplace Spirituality and Management Recognition	.555	Very High Workplace Spirituality
Workplace Spirituality and Promotion	.703	Very High Workplace Spirituality
Workplace Spirituality and Nature of Work	-.384	Very High Workplace Spirituality
Workplace Spirituality and Benefits and Rewards	.406	Very High Workplace Spirituality

Conclusion and Recommendations

In terms of job satisfaction, the respondents reported that the most important factor that affects their job satisfaction is compensation. As employees, they are still primarily looking for their welfare, specifically the payment they received from the organization. The results worth noting are that the second and third influential factors for teachers were the relationships they have with their managers, supervisors, and co-workers. This means that it is vital for employees to have a harmonious relationship with the members of the organization. They believe that work becomes more enjoyable and pleasurable if the people around them have their own values and beliefs. In terms of workplace spirituality, employees reported that they experience a very high workplace spirituality working in the institution. The employees see that the people and the whole community transcend feeling and compassion in the four (4) corners of the organization. However, the faculty has also seen that it is vital for the organization to prioritize the welfare of its employees. This may be attributed to the vast responsibilities included in the usual workload of the faculty, such as accreditation and out-of-school activities. In terms of the relationship between workplace spirituality and factors affecting the job satisfaction of the faculty, an area for further improvement was the relationship between workplace spirituality and training and development. It seems that employees perceive that workplace spirituality is not affected by attending or sending them to seminars.

Managers and supervisors may still improve the current faculty line-up by hiring highly competent and experienced teachers, particularly those belonging to the female population. This may help in addressing issues related to gender sensitivity and equality. The human resources department may look into the current compensation that each SHSP faculty member receives. Proper remuneration must be given to faculty, particularly those who are highly competent with supporting credentials such as educational background and experience. Furthermore, the department may create programs or services that will further motivate and challenge the faculty. These programs or services may entail recognition and corresponding rewards that may result in job satisfaction and improve employees' performance. The organization must be able to prioritize the welfare of the employees by attending to their needs, particularly making them feel that they are very welcome working in the institution. Improving the current and existing workplace spirituality, particularly at the organizational level, will help employees feel that they are working in the right place and for the right institution.

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